

Public Health and Education for a Sustainable Future: How Climate Change Affects Community Health and Ways to Adapt: A Review

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Abstract

This uses a scientific method, particularly meta-synthesis, to examine how community human living areas are affected by climate change. Throughout the evaluation process, the researcher mostly uses deductive reasoning because climate change is a global subject with broad ramifications. A thorough archive analysis was part of the research plan, which was followed by a thorough examination of pertinent documents. This review article's methodology involves a comprehensive analysis and assessment of national and international sources, including reports from the World Health Organization (WHO), the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), national statistics, and annual publications from Nepal's Department of Health Services, among other relevant materials. This method, which draws from a wide variety of reliable sources, guarantees a thorough and methodical grasp of the subject.

Children were impacted by the flood and the consequences of climate change-related natural floods. Children in the Karnali floods are more malnourished than children in the non-flood-affected sane socioeconomic region. Increasing mental health issues, worse health outcomes for mothers and new-borns, increasing water insecurity, and an increased caregiving burden are some of the specific effects of climate change.

Hospitals are closed due to heavy rainfall, power outages, injuries, mental health disorders, stress, gastrointestinal and vector-borne illnesses, aggravation of chronic illnesses, low birth weight and premature births, a decline in the quality and potential disruption of health services, and an increase in demand for health services. Waterborne diseases including cholera, malaria, and diarrheal ailments thrive when water and sanitation systems are disrupted by flooding. Communities are uprooted and agricultural infrastructure is destroyed by flooding, which exacerbates food insecurity and malnutrition.

Floods, droughts, landslides, heat waves, and cold waves are all major effects of climate change in Nepal. With glaciers melting and upsetting the hydrological cycle, it has additional implications on human health, agriculture, hydropower, economic losses, displacement, and ecological risks.

In the future, sustainable development and climate change adaptation will employ the following strategies. To lessen susceptibility and increase resilience to extreme weather, these include strengthening infrastructure, managing water better, upgrading early warning systems, and changing policies.

Keywords: *adaptation, climate change, community, flood, health facility and health personal, public health*